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OLONITE TWO- THIRD-POINT-FIVE RULE (OLONITE 2/3.5 RULE)

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ABSTRACT

Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (O2/3.5R) is a selection rule employed to reduce the stress of researchers who are to sample a large population while maintaining the optimal selection from the large population. Using a three sampling/selection techniques, the result showed that the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule gives a more flexible result for researchers as seen in table 1. The rule provides the most precision for estimating a population as it supports the 1/2 and 2/3 rule. Olonite Rule is always the best rule when a population is large and a researcher must sample the required size taking into consideration, the optimum sampling size which should be half of the total population and a little bit above. The rule states: "the closer a sample size to its total population, the more reliance the result". The rule is recommended to be used all over institutions and world. It is time to appreciate the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule in Academics and for sampling purposes.

Keywords: Olonite Sampling Technique, OST, Taro Yamane Sampling Method, Olonite Rule, Olonite 2/3.5 Rule, O2/3.5R

INTRODUCTION

Statistics has experienced great developments since its inception. It exposed us to many sampling techniques, methods, selection, regression analysis and others. The two third Rule (2/3) usage can be seen from different sphere of the world e.g. Political, Military, Governance, Voting, etc however it has not been appreciated in the academics and research.

The $2/3$ rule is a political principle requiring that two thirds rather than a simple majority of the members of a politically organized group must concur in order to exercise the power to make decisions binding upon the whole group. In the Military, the $1/3$, $2/3$ rule states that Commanders should use one-third of the time available before mission execution for their planning while allocating the remaining two-thirds to their subordinates for simultaneous preparation (Merriam-Webster, 2021).

The two-thirds rule is used at all levels of government and in many social and political organizations to prevent the dominance of a small majority over a large minority. The U.S. Constitution, for example, gives the Senate sole authority to ratify treaties proposed by the President of the United States and to try impeachments but makes this contingent upon a two thirds majority, thus ensuring broad support for such important measures. In 1832, the Democratic Party adopted a two-thirds rule for nominating a presidential candidate. Frequent attempts to change the rule were resisted by those who believed it to be a convenient tool to prevent a candidacy they opposed (Bass, H. F., 1988).

Since much focus has not been on the 2.3 rule in academics and research, it was modified to Olonite $2/3.5$ Rule to make sampling from a large population reasonably done since it selects 50% of the total population plus a little addition; for example, a researcher sampling 2365 respondents out of a population of 212123 is not ideal since the result will not be closer to reality. The Rule asserts that the higher the rule denominator, the decrease the sample size to the total population. Since $\frac{1}{2}$ of the total population is achieved, the “.5” is added to the “3” to increase while adding to the $\frac{1}{2}$ population but far below the total population.

Sampling 121213 from a total population of 212123 using the Olonite $2/3.5$ Rule ($O2/3.5R$) is better since it gives a researcher the possibility of sampling flexibly (Sampling above the total

Population half and yet not closer to the total population) but sampling 198936 from a total population of 212123 using the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) is best since it is at optimal.

Table 1. Olonite Sampling Technique, Taro Yamane Sampling Method and the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule

Organization	Population	Olonite Sampling Technique	Taro Yamane Sampling Method	Olonite 2/3.5 Rule
A	14856	13932	390	8489
B	17377	16297	391	9930
C	42013	39401	396	24007
D	26073	24452	394	14899
E	75883	71166	398	43362
F	35921	33688	396	20526
OVERALL TOTAL	212123	198936	2365	121213

Source: Author's Design and Computation, 2021

Olonite Sampling Technique (Formulae): $SS = \frac{TP}{1 + TP(TCL - OCL/100)^3}$

Note: SS = Sampling Size

TP = Total Population

1 = Booster or Step-down

μ = Stochastic Error

^{3,4,5,6 and 7} = Multiplier

TCL = Total Confidence Level

OCL = Observed Confidence Level

$$SS_A = \frac{14856}{1 + 14856(0.05)^3} = 13932$$

$$SS_B = \frac{17377}{1 + 17377(0.05)^3} = 16297$$

$$SS_C = \frac{42013}{1 + 42013(0.05)^3} = 39401$$

$$SS_D = \frac{26073}{1 + 26073(0.05)^3} = 24452$$

$$SS_E = \frac{75883}{1 + 75883(0.05)^3} = 71166$$

$$SS_F = \frac{35921}{1 + 35921(0.05)^3} = 33688$$

Taro Yamane Sampling Method (Formulae):

$$\frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Note: N = Total Population
e = Error Term/Epsilon

$$A = \frac{14856}{1 + 14856(0.05)^2} = 390$$

$$B = \frac{17377}{1 + 17377(0.05)^2} = 391$$

$$C = \frac{42013}{1 + 42013(0.05)^2} = 396$$

$$D = \frac{26073}{1 + 26073(0.05)^2} = 394$$

$$E = \frac{75883}{1 + 75883(0.05)^2} = 398$$

$$F = \frac{35921}{1 + 35921(0.05)^2} = 396$$

Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (Formulae): $\frac{2}{3.5} \times TP$

$$A = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 14856 = 8489$$

$$B = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 17377 = 9930$$

$$C = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 42013 = 24007$$

$$D = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 26073 = 14899$$

$$E = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 75883 = 43362$$

$$F = \frac{2}{3.5} \times 35921 = 20526$$

4. DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the result of the three selection methods the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST), Taro Yamane Sampling Method and the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule. For Organisation A with a population of 14856, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 13932 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 390 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 8489.

For Organisation B with a population of 17377, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 16297 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 391 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 9930.

For Organisation C with a population of 42013, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 39401 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 396 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 24007.

For Organisation D with a population of 26073, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 24452 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 394 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 14899.

For Organisation E with a population of 75883, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 71166 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 398 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 43362.

For Organisation F with a population of 35921, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 33688 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 396 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 20526.

For Organisation A-F with a total population of 212123, Olonite Sampling Technique shows a sample size of 198936 should be used; Taro Yamane shows a sample size of 2365 while Olonite 2/3.5 Rule shows a sample size result of 121213.

As it can be seen in each method, The Olonite Sampling Method (OST) has the highest sample size of 198936, follows by the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule having 121213 while the Taro Yamane Sampling Method shows a sample size of 2365. Olonite 2/3.5 Rule submits a more flexible sample size as it is above the half of the total population while the Taro Yamane is far below the half.

A researcher sampling 2365 respondents out of a population of 212123 is not ideal since the result will not be closer to reality. However, sampling 121213 from a total population of 212123 using the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (O2/3.5R) is better since it gives a researcher the possibility of sampling flexibly (Sampling above the total Population half and yet not closer to the total

population) but sampling 198936 from a total population of 212123 using the Olonite Sampling Technique (OST) is best since it is at optimal.

5. CONCLUSION

Olonite 2/3.5 Rule (O2/3.5R) is a selection rule employed to reduce the stress of researchers who are to sample a large population while maintaining the optimal selection from the large population. Using a three sampling/selection techniques, the result showed that the Olonite 2/3.5 Rule gives a more flexible result for researchers as seen in table 1. The rule provides the most precision for estimating a population as it supports the 1/2 and 2/3 rule. Olonite Rule is always the best rule when a population is large and a researcher must sample the required size taking into consideration, the optimum sampling size which should be half of the total population and a little bit above. The rule also state: “the closer a sample size to its total population, the more reliance the result”.

6. RECOMMENDATION

i. As seen in the Table 1, where The Olonite 2/3.5 Rule result is less than each organization’s sample size as in comparison with the Olonite Sampling Technique but higher than the sample size of the Taro Yamane Sampling Method, O2/3.5R is encouraged to be used in Academics, Statistics Departments, by Countries, Governments, Organizations, Researchers, Research Departments, Universities, States, etc.

ii. For large population, the researcher should opt for an online response collation and not the administration of hard copy questionnaires since it saves time and energy.

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